

Foliage acclimatization to variable light conditions integrates adjustments in plant morphology and physiology in *Polyscias filicifolia*

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ABSTRACT

Foliage ornamentals are classified as “shade plants” and “sun plants” by growers based on their light requirement. As a result, people tend to be more selective in growing foliage ornamentals. *Polyscias filicifolia* is a popular foliage ornamental which is regarded as a plant preferring partial shade. If this plant can be acclimatized in to different light environments with beneficial changes in plant architecture, it would massively benefit the industry. This study was conducted to assess the acclimatization potential of *Polyscias filicifolia* to variable light conditions and to study its morphological and physiological adjustments. Selected plants were grown in plastic pots of 15 cm diameter in a standard foliage plant medium. Plants were exposed to different light levels as four treatments. Namely, full sunlight (open), 50% shade (green nets), 50% shade (black nets) and 80% shade (black nets). For shading purpose, available commercial black polypropylene shade nets and common garden green shade nets were used. Growth and morphological measurements of leaf, root, stem and whole plant were recorded at 100 days after planting. Results of the study revealed significant differences in leaf growth, leaf morphology, plant height, stem and root growth among different treatments, depicting the phenotypic plasticity of *Polyscias filicifolia*. Plants grown under black shade nets were more aesthetically appealing. It can be concluded that *Polyscias filicifolia* has the potential to be acclimatized in to variable light conditions with adjustments in plant morphology and physiology.

Keywords: acclimatization, phenotypic plasticity. *Polyscias filicifolia*

INTRODUCTION

Light is the major environmental condition that affects the plant growth and development. Plants response to light quality, quantity, direction and periodicity (Stamps, 2009). Therefore, plants that grow in different light environments have specific light requirements. The plant’s ability to acclimate to different light environments includes alterations both at leaf level, associated with morphological, anatomical and physiological characteristics and at the whole-plant level, which is mainly related to shoot architecture and biomass allocation patterns (Poorter, 2001). This phenomenon is also called as phenotypic plasticity in plants in response to light. Phenotypic plasticity is defined as plant’s ability to change its morphology, physiology and behavior according to

environmental conditions (West-Eberhard, 1989, Schlichting, 1986).

The genus *Polyscias* that belongs to family Araliaceae, is a widely growing ornamental plant in Southeastern Asia and in the Pacific region. It is an ornamental foliage shrub having yellow-green foliage that is extensively used in landscaping (Whistler, 2000). Light intensity has a considerable influence on its variegation patterns thus having a high demand in the export market in Sri Lanka. *Polyscias* is considered as a shade loving tropical foliage that prefers high temperature and humidity therefore, partial shade has been recommended for the cultivation in Sri Lanka (Krishnamoorthy et al., 2020, Thanusha et al., 2020).

Almost all the ornamental plants have been categorized in to different categories based on

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their light requirement. There is a belief in people that, 'shade plants' (i.e. shade loving plants) cannot be grown in sun and 'sun plants' (i.e. sun loving plants) cannot be grown in shade with success. Due to this reason, people tend to be more selective in growing ornamental plants. However, if this can be disproved, surely the ornamental plant growers will be benefited. Acclimatizing to different light environment demands changes in pigment count, enzymes, resource allocation and leaf anatomy (Middleton, 2001). In the ornamental plant context, the change in the plant form by any means is a momentous concern. Nevertheless, changes in the plant architecture which favors the progress of the industry, has a commercial value.

To date, most comprehensive studies have evaluated growth of forest tree seedlings at different irradiance levels (Poorter, 1999). However, in the past studies, a little attempt has been made to identify the light acclimatization potential of ornamental foliage plants. Therefore, this study was carried out to test the following hypotheses; (i) foliage ornamental plants can be acclimatized to different light environments, (ii) light acclimatization potential of ornamental foliage plants will be displayed within a few months after exposure and (iii) foliage acclimatization to variable light conditions integrates adjustments in plant morphology and physiology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was carried out in a semi-open greenhouse located in the Mid Country Wet Zone in Sri Lanka. Width-wise sides of the greenhouse were kept open while length-wise sides were covered with a white netting to reduce the heat building up inside the greenhouse. The top of the greenhouse was covered with UV resistant polyethylene film.

Similar-sized and similar-aged, vegetatively propagated, ready-to-ship, export quality *Polyscias filicifolia* (L.) H.A.T. Harms plants were used for the study. The selected plants were grown in plastic pots of 15 cm diameter. The medium used was the standard medium for foliage plants (loam soil 4: compost 2: cattle

manure 1: sand 1) recommended by the Department of National Botanic Gardens, Sri Lanka. The plants were fertilized with a 20:20:20 mixture (Cultisol F60® – Bower & Co) once every month and an organic fertilizer (Maxicrop® – LANKEM) every two weeks. All the plants were watered depending on the moisture depletion.

In this experiment, plants were exposed to different light levels as four treatments. For shading purpose, available commercial black polypropylene shade nets and the common garden green shade net which is popular among home gardeners in Sri Lanka were used; Full sunlight (open – T1), Garden green shade net with 50% Shade (green – T2), Commercial 50 % black shade net (50 % - T3) and Commercial 80 % black shade net (80 % - T4).

The terminal leaf of all plants was marked at the beginning to observe the subsequent growth easily. The leaf, stem, root and overall plant growth-related parameters were measured at the time of field planting and thereafter 100 days of planting. Based on the measured parameters, mass ratios and specific weight ratios were calculated. Aesthetic quality was also assessed as proposed by Conover (1986).

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for quantitative variables from measurements, was used for testing the treatment differences. Mean separation was carried out by using Duncan's New Multiple Range Test to facilitate all possible comparisons. Qualitative data of aesthetic evaluation were analyzed using Kruskal-Wallis test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in the Table 1, different shade levels and shade net colours (Black and green) had a significant ($p < 0.05$) effect on the leaf area of *Polyscias filicifolia* plants. Plants grown under 50% and 80% commercial black shade nets (T3 and T4) recorded a significantly higher average leaf area (ALA) compared to that of plants grown under full sunlight (T1). These results are in line with the findings of other studies conducted using tropical forest species *Polyscias fulva* (Kinyamario et al., 2008). It indicates that, plants responded to shade by increasing their leaf areas. This can be identified as an adaptation to

shade (Vincent, 2006). Plants grown under 50% commercial black shade nets (T3), recorded significantly higher ALA compared to that of 80% commercial black shade nets (T4). Similar studies have revealed that leaf areas of plants vary with the amount of light received (Kriebitzsch et al., 1997; Takahashi and Rustandi, 2006). The 80% black shade might be cutting down too much light for the optimum leaf growth of *Polyscias filicifolia*. Similar observations have been made on studies conducted using *Polyscias balfouriana* L. var. 'Marginata' and *Polyscias guilfoylei variegata* (Thanusha et al., 2020,

Krishnamoorthy et al., 2020). However, plants grown under green shade net with 50% Shade (T2) recorded significantly lower ALA compared to other treatments. Color of the shade net predominantly affects light quality, light intensity, temperature and RH. Green shade nets typically exhibit higher light intensity, temperature and lower RH compared to that of the microclimate under black shade nets (Gaurav et al., 2016). Results of this study indicates that, these microclimatic variations under the green color shade nets reduces the ALA of *Polyscias filicifolia* compared to black shade nets.

Table 1: Means of leaf growth and morphology measures of *Polyscias filicifolia* as affected by different light levels at 100 days after planting.^a

	Green	Open	50 %	80 %
Number of leaves	39	41	32	34
Length (cm)	15.84±0.92c	14.8±0.86d	16.92±1.01b	19.28±0.93a
Width (cm)	13.75±0.68b	14.22±0.91b	16.1±0.87a	15.64±0.79a
Total leaf area (cm ²)	545±6c	825±4b	855±8ba	870±8a
Average leaf area (cm ²)	13.97±0.056d	20.12±0.059c	26.72±0.84a	25.59±0.67b
Total leaf dry weight (mg)	2085.3±35.6b	1400.8±31.1c	2271.3±29.7a	2301.7±32.5a
Average leaf weight (mg)	53.5±1.12c	34.2±1.1d	71.0±1.31a	67.7±1.17b
Leaf weight ratio	0.32	0.28	0.39	0.38
Specific leaf area (cm ² /mg)	0.261	0.589	0.376	0.378
Specific leaf weight (mg/cm ²)	3.83	1.7	2.66	2.65
Chlorophyll (SPAD value)	19.11±0.48ba	18.56±0.75b	19.55±0.59a	17.46±0.69c

^a Means across different shade levels sharing the same letter are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$ level. ($n=5$)

Plants grown in open condition (T1) recorded the lowest leaf weight ratio (LWR), indicating lower leaf biomass with respect to plant biomass. Plants grown under shade (T2, T3 and T4) recorded a higher LWR resulting in larger canopies. Even though the ALA of T2 was lower than that of T1, under the green shade, plants have produced more leaf biomass compared to open conditions. Largest canopies were recorded under the black shade nets perhaps due to the lower light intensity, temperature and higher RH under black color shade nets. These results are in agreement with the past studies that recorded similar effects on plant processes under black shade nets (Smith et al., 1983).

Specific leaf area (SLA) was higher in the plants grown under open conditions (T1) indicating thinner leaves. Plants grown under shade (T2, T3 and T4) recorded thicker leaves. These changes in SLA under shade and open conditions requires important anatomical changes in leaf mesophyll and palisade layers (Kinyamario et al., 2008). Similar changes in leaf anatomical and biochemical Structure have been observed in previous studies (Oguchi et al., 2008, Vincent, 2006). SLA in the plants grown under green shade net was lower than that of the plants grown under black shade nets. Lower light intensity, temperature and higher RH under black color shade net could be the reason for that.

SPAD value is an indirect measurement on the leaf chlorophyll content. SPAD values of plants grown under 50% shade in both green garden nets and commercial black color nets (T2 and T3) recorded significantly higher SPAD values compared to that of plants in the open (T1). Similar results have been reported in studies conducted using cordyline plants (Gaurav et al., 2016). Costa et al., (2010), have reported more numerous and larger chloroplasts in plants grown under shade. Previous studies have shown that Photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) and transmittance levels are significantly lower under shade nets compared to open environments (Gaurav et al., 2016) resulting higher chlorophyll content in the plants grown under shade. However, there was no significant difference in the SPAD measurement of T2 and T3. This is also in line with the results of Gaurav et al., (2016), who reported no significant difference among the chlorophyll content of plants grown under different color shade nets. Lowest chlorophyll content was recorded in the plants grown under 80% shade commercial black color nets (T4). Importantly, it was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower than the SPAD value recorded in plants grown in open conditions (T1). PAR and transmittance levels are significantly lower under black shade nets compared to green shade nets (Gaurav et al., 2016). However, with no significant difference among T2 and T3, it can be mainly the effect of excess shade at 80% shade level that has affected the chlorophyll content of plants.

According to Table 2 results, the different light levels have a significant influence on the root growth and morphology measures of *Polyscias filicifolia*. Root length was significantly higher in the open treatment (T1). Higher light intensities result in higher root growth rates (Bethlenfalvay and Pacovsky, 1983). All the other three treatments (T2, T3, T4) showed lower root growth rates mainly because their light intensities were lower than T1. Regardless of the net colour, lower light intensities could be observed compared to open sunlight conditions (Stamps, 2009). Root lengths were lower in T4

and T3 respectively. Black shade nets are able to decrease the light intensity without harming the quality of the light and on the other hand, coloured nets (green) modify the spectrum of light which can influence plant development and growth (Castellano et al., 2008, Shahak et al., 2008). The possible lower light intensities could be the reason behind the lower root growth rates followed by lower root dry weights in T3 and T4 compared to T1 and T2. Lower root growth rates also can result in higher investments on shoot growth (Bethlenfalvay and Pacovsky, 1983). Hence, lower root weight ratios were observed in T3 and T4 compared to T1 and T2.

Different shade levels influenced the internodal length of *Polyscias filicifolia* (Table 3). Internodal length was found to be highest under garden shade net with 50% shade (green), followed by 80%, 50% black shade and it was lowest under full sunlight. Total stem dry weight was found to be significantly higher under green and there was no significant difference in total stem dry weight under 50% and 80% black shade. It was the lowest under full sunlight. Stem diameter was found to be maximum under 80% black shade and the lowest stem diameter was observed under 50% black shade. Highest stem weight ratio was observed under full sunlight followed by 50% green shade. It was found to be the lowest stem weight ratio and was on par with 50% and 80% black shade. 50% shade level under garden shade recorded the highest internodal length and total stem dry weight. The internodal length and total dry weight declined at higher shade levels. Dudley and Schmitt (1995) found that the foliage plants grown under shade had more elongated internodes than the plants grown in open areas or under higher shades. Bibi et al., (2012), made similar observations. Hlatshwayo and Wahome, (2010), have also presented supportive results by observing taller plants when grown under partial shade. The superior performance at 50% green shade level may be due to higher leaf chlorophyll content and photosynthetic rate.

Table 2: Means of root growth and morphology measures of *Polyscias filicifolia* as affected by different light levels at 100 days after planting. ^a

	Green	Open	50 %	80 %
Length (cm)	488.92±16.8b	600.22±19.2a	337.82±14.6d	405.66±14.2c
Total root dry weight (mg)	1181.2±22.7a	987.4±17.1b	766.2±17.9d	881.3±20.9c
Root weight ratio	0.18	0.19	0.13	0.14

^a Means across different shade levels sharing the same letter are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$ level. ($n=5$)

Table 3: Means of stem growth and morphology measures of *Polyscias filicifolia* as affected by different light levels at 100 days after planting. ^a

	Green	Open	50 %	80 %
Internodal Length (cm)	1.74±0.22	1.37±0.29	1.46±0.27	1.62±0.31
Total stem dry weight (mg)	3240.2a	2689.4c	2859.2b	2937.3b
New stem	961.5	769.8	988.4	971.6
Mother wood	2278.7	1919.6	1870.8	1965.7
Stem diameter (mm)	0.625±0.01b	0.61±0.01b	0.572±0.02c	0.712±0.01a
Stem weight ratio	0.50	0.53	0.48	0.48

^a Means across different shade levels sharing the same letter are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$ level. ($n=5$)

Table 4: Means of overall growth and morphology measures of *Polyscias filicifolia* as affected by different light levels at 100 days after planting. ^a

	Green	Open	50 %	80 %
Plant height (cm)	15.7±1.25b	12.35±1.01c	16.7±1.34a	16.4±1.44ba
Total dry weight (mg)	6506.7±50.7	5077.6±54.3	5896.7±69.5	6120.3±67.5
Relative growth rate (mg/g/day)	11.7	9.9	11.0	11.3
Root: Shoot ratio	0.222	0.241	0.149	0.168
Aesthetic evaluation	78.5±2.5	74.5±2.41	88.5±2.8	87±2.73

^a Means across different shade levels sharing the same letter are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$ level. ($n=5$)

Plant heights were significantly higher in T3 and T4 (Table 4). Shading effects of the black nets can result in lower evapotranspiration and plant water stress, resulting improved rates of photosynthesis and carbohydrate production thus increasing vegetative growth (Iglesias and Alegre, 2006). Comparatively lower values for total dry weight and relative growth rate were achieved in T1 possibly due to lower

photosynthetic rates resulted by high temperature, evapotranspiration, stress conditions and stomatal closing (Kalcsits et al., 2017, Tanny et al., 2008, Stamps, 2009, Jutamane and Onnom, 2016). Lower root:shoot ratio could be observed in T3 and T4. It may be due to higher photosynthetic rates which cause better vegetative growth under black shade. Usually shade plants have smaller stomata

volume, larger chloroplast and greater proportion of chlorophyll *b* to chlorophyll *a* than chloroplasts of high-light plants. According to the Prasad and Kumar, (2003), increased number of chloroplasts caused for increased light absorption. In shade plants, resistance to chlorophyll concentration is increased by the resistance to chlorophyll degradation. Gunadasa and Dissanayake (2012) found that, as a result of synthesis of more chlorophyll *a* and *b* in the leaves of foliage plants, the color development takes place. Moreover, with increasing shade level, the chlorophyll content is also increased. Hence, significantly higher scores have been achieved by T4 and T3 in the aesthetic evaluation.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that *Polyscias filicifolia* has the potential to be acclimatized in to different light conditions. In addition, *Polyscias filicifolia* displays its acclimatization potential within few months after the exposure to various light environments. Foliage acclimatization to variable light conditions of *Polyscias filicifolia* integrates adjustments in plant morphology and physiology.

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